

D4.3 – Report on living tissues issues affecting light propagation

StretchBio – Report on living tissues issues affecting light propagation

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Abstract:	This deliverable reports the experimental results of growing tissues and cells on top of nanopillar arrays and analysing whether this growth proceeds by penetrating between the nanopillars and whether this has an impact in the light transmission through the photonic system. The results show that even though the tissues and cells develop cilia that extend over several tens of micrometres across the nanopillar array surface, they only penetrate vertically around 100 nm. This result is almost general for all type of tissues, biopsies or cell types analysed. Little effects on light transmission have been observed, probably due to the fact that the light propagates through the central part of the upper section of the nanopillars and waveguides.

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the experimental findings concerning the growth of tissues and cells on nanopillar arrays, assessing whether this growth occurs by infiltrating between the nanopillars and examining its influence on light transmission within the photonic system. The results indicate that although tissues and cells develop cilia extending over several tens of micrometres across the surface of the nanopillar array, their vertical penetration is limited to around 100 nm.

This observation holds true across various tissue types, biopsies, and cell varieties analysed. Minimal effects on light transmission have been noted, likely attributable to the propagation of light through the central portion of the upper section of the nanopillars and waveguides.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope of the document

This document outlines the observed effects of growing tissues and cells atop nanopillar arrays and examines how this growth impacts light transmission through the photonic system. To achieve this, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) is utilized on dried samples to visualize these effects and offer guidance for the continued development of the nanosystem.

1.2 Related documents

The biocompatibility and adhesion studies involving the same cell types and *Drosophila melanogaster* epithelia utilized in this document have been comprehensively detailed in reports D4.1 and D4.2, thus establishing a direct correlation with the present report.

The fabrication methodology utilized for creating the nanopillar arrays is described in report D3.3, although a modified version of this approach was employed in this document.

Regarding the light transmission measurements during cell and tissue culture, the nanosystems utilized align with those documented in report D5.3.

2 Cell, tissue and biopsy growth on top of nanopillar arrays

2.1 Cell, tissue and biopsy growth methods, nanopillar arrays in silicon substrates, and preparation of samples for electron microscopy observations

The cell and tissue types utilized in this document are enumerated in Table 1. They correspond to those employed in the biocompatibility and adhesion studies documented in deliverables D4.1 and D4.2, with their usage justified therein. Specifically, report D4.1 delineates the growth conditions for these cell lines and tissues, conditions which were replicated for the present report. However, in this study, we fabricated nanopillar arrays using a combination of deep ultraviolet (DUV) lithography, metal deposition, lift-off, and reactive ion etching techniques on silicon substrates. The choice of employing DUV lithography in the fabrication process, instead of the electron beam lithography detailed in deliverable D3.3, stems from the former's parallel fabrication capability. This enables the patterning of large nanopillar-based arrays over extended areas in 150 mm in diameter silicon wafers in short times, thereby enhancing throughput and expediting interfacing experiments.

It is noteworthy that, due to the availability of an existing mask for DUV lithography containing square-shaped nanopillar arrays, as opposed to the hexagonal distribution outlined in deliverable D3.3, most of the reported growth results were obtained on substrates of such nature. For the light transmission experiments, we utilized the photonic nanosystem structures documented in deliverable D6.1.

Table 1: Cell and tissue types employed in this work to test the growth and interaction with the nanopillar array

Cell/tissue type	Origin
Caco-2	Human colonic adenocarcima
A-594	Human lung adenocarcinoma
NCI-H358	Human brochioalveolar carcinoma
Imaginal discs	<i>Drosophila melanogaster</i>

After the growth of cells or tissues, samples are prepared for inspection inside a scanning electron microscope (SEM) or for cross-section cutting inside a focused ion beam (FIB) machine coupled to a SEM, ensuring the preservation of their geometry and topography.

This preparation involves several steps:

1. Chemical fixation: Formaldehyde is introduced into the cells or tissues to fix them in place.
2. Dehydration: Water is extracted from the samples and replaced with ethanol.

3. Critical point drying: Liquid ethanol is removed while preserving the integrity of cells or tissues.
4. Gold coating: A thin layer of gold is sputter-coated onto the sample surface, aiding in electron discharge during SEM imaging.

2.2 Structural characterisation using SEM/FIB

SEM images of A-549 and NCI-H358 lung cancer cells grown on top of nanopillar arrays are shown in Figure 1. For both types of cells, the formation of pro-adhesion structures is clearly evidenced, which is in agreement with the demonstrated cell viability presented and discussed in report D4.1.

Branched filopodia

Peripheral cytoplasm ruffling

Figure 1. SEM images of different types of cells grown on top of nanopillar arrays, showing the direct contact between cells and nanopillar, as well as the formation of pro-adhesion structures. Left: A-549 cells showing filopodia. Right: NCI-H358 cells, presenting cytoplasm ruffling

Similar growth patterns have been observed for colorectal cancer cells Caco-2. The images presented in Figure 2 depict Caco-2 cells cultivated for 4 and 72 hours atop the nanopillar arrays. In both instances, a focused ion beam (FIB) was utilized to prepare cross-sections, facilitating observation of the cell and nanopillar interfaces. This method enables the identification of the nanopillar structure, which remains distinctly visible, particularly evident in the lower right image. Additionally, the lower right image reveals a certain degree of penetration of the pro-adhesion structures into the vacant space between the individual nanopillars, estimated to be around 100 nm.

It is important to note that, as per the simulations conducted in WP2, light transmission primarily occurs within the central portion rather than the top of the nanopillars. Consequently, the anticipated impact on light transmission is expected to be minimal.

Figure 2. Cross-sectional SEM images of Caco-2 cells obtained inside a FIB machine for 4 hours (top) and 72 hours (bottom) grown cells. The right images (B and D) are a high magnification of the left images (A and C). A limited penetration of the pro-adhesion cellular structure in the inter-pillar space can be observed.

Analogous growth and characterisation experiments have been performed with imaginal disks from wing epithelia of *Drosophila melanogaster* larvae, whose results are shown in Figure 3. In the upper figure (A) the whole imaginal disk can be seen, at whose front part the FIB cut has been performed, indicated by the red box. Figure 3 B) and C) show two low magnification cross-section images of this cut, taken at two different regions, while Figure 3 D) and E) are higher magnification images of samples in Figure 3 B) and C), respectively. Especially in Figure 3 E) the integrity of the nanopillars is evidenced, which proves that the pillars are not negatively affected by the SEM preparation method. Similarly to Similar growth patterns have been observed for colorectal cancer cells Caco-2. The images presented in Figure 2 depict Caco-2 cells cultivated for 4 and 72 hours atop the nanopillar arrays. In both instances, a focused ion beam (FIB) was utilized to prepare cross-sections, facilitating observation of the cell and nanopillar interfaces. This method enables the identification of the nanopillar structure, which remains distinctly visible, particularly evident in the lower right image. Additionally, the lower right image reveals a certain degree of penetration of the pro-adhesion structures into the vacant space between the individual nanopillars, estimated to be around 100 nm.

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Figure 2, the penetration of the cellular tissue structure in the inter-pillar space is estimated to be in the range of 100 nm.

Additionally, we conducted tests involving human lung adenocarcinoma (ADC) biopsy samples to assess their adhesion to the silicon nanopillars over a 48-hour period before SEM preparation. Our observations revealed a physical attachment of the tissue to the nanopillars, akin to the adhesion observed with individual cells.

Figure 3. Cross-sectional SEM images of imaginal disks of *Drosophila melanogaster* obtained inside a FIB machine. A) the complete imaginal disk in which the front part, indicated by the red box has been prepared by FIB. B) through E) cross-sectional images show the limited penetration of the cellular structure in the inter-pillar space

Figure 4: SEM images from an ADC tumor from human patient. Left: ADC adhere on nanopillars. Right: ADC tumors develop filopodial structures which attach to the nanopillars.

2.3 Light transmission through the waveguide

In this section, the effect of cell and tissue growth and placement on top of the chip containing the nanosensor and the accessing waveguides is presented. In the case of the former, solutions with different concentration of cells have been prepared and deposited on top of the nanopillar array. This can be seen in Figure 5 that shows the light propagation through the waveguide, which is monitored using the microscope equipped with an infrared camera and which is placed on top of the nanosensor.

It is evident that for this image, which corresponds to a solution containing a low concentration of Caco-2 cells, there is enough light passing through the whole waveguide, with enough intensity reaching the waveguide's output. If the concentration of cells is increased, the light propagation is dimmed and vanishes with a high concentration of cells.

Figure 5. Effective light propagation through the waveguide contained in the photonic chip while a low concentration of cells is placed on top of it

Similar experiments have been performed with the *Drosophila melanogaster* imaginal disks. Again, in this case, the disks have been extracted from the larvae and placed directly on top of the chip using the available microscope, as shown in the top of Figure 6. The lower image presents the light transmission through the waveguide while the tissue is still on top of the photonic crystal, while in its inset the light emitted through the side is monitored using an external photodetector.

Figure 6. Top: researcher placing the *Drosophila melanogaster* imaginal disk on top of the photonic chip, controlling the process with the microscope. Bottom: Image obtained using the infrared camera coupled to the microscope, showing the light transmission through the waveguide. The left inset shows the light collected at the exit of the waveguide, proving that enough light reaches the end of the waveguide

3 Conclusions

This deliverable presents the outcomes of cultivating various types of cancer cell lines, *Drosophila melanogaster* imaginal discs and human lung adenocarcinoma biopsies on silicon substrates featuring large area nanopillar arrays. This investigation aimed to analyse the adhesion artifacts produced and visualize the extent of penetration into the inter-pillar spacing.

The findings indicate that such penetration is confined to the first 100 nm from the top of the nanopillars and is anticipated to have no adverse effects on light propagation through the nanosensor and the waveguide. This assertion is further validated through experimental assessment of light transmission with cells or tissues atop the arrays. Notably, for tissues, only minimal attenuation of light is observed, representing a promising outcome for the project's subsequent phases. Similarly, for cells, this holds true provided that the cell concentration in the deposited solution on the chip remains low. However, in cases of high cell concentrations, light propagation through the waveguide is hindered, thus establishing an upper limit for practical applications.

4 Glossary

Abbreviation	Explanation
DX.Y	Deliverable X.Y
DUV	Deep Ultraviolet Lithography
FIB	Focused Ion Beam
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscope
ADC	Adenocarcinoma
SiO ₂	Silicon Dioxide

[END OF THE DOCUMENT]

